

Table 1. Effect of green manure (GM), mungbean residues, maize fodder, and N application on rice grain yield (t/ha). Ludhiana, India, 1984-85.

Crop grown before rice	Grain yield (t/ha)			
	0	60	120	180
		kg N	kg N	kg N
Fallow	2.5	4.6	5.6	6.6
Sesbania GM	5.8	6.4	—	—
Cowpea (GM)	6.0	6.8	—	—
Sunn hemp (GM)	5.8	6.8	—	—
Mungbean (pulse)	5.1	6.2	—	—
Maize (fodder)	2.2	4.5	5.7	6.5
LSD (P=0.05)	0.7			

Table 2. Residual effect of GM, mungbean residues, and maize fodder grown before rice on succeeding wheat crop. Ludhiana, India, 1984-85.

Crop grown before rice	N applied to wheat (kg/ha)	Wheat yield (t/ha)
Fallow	120	4.7
Sesbania (GM)	90	4.3
Cowpea (GM)	90	4.2
Sunn hemp	90	4.1
Mungbean (pulse)	90	4.2
Maize (fodder)	120	4.9
LSD (P=0.05)		0.4

after transplanting). A basal dose of 13-13 kg PK/ha was applied. The residual effect of these treatments was studied on the succeeding dry season wheat crop.

At 60 d growth, sesbania and sunn hemp had produced the most dry matter (4.9 and 5.3 t/ha), followed by cowpea and mungbean (3.8 and 3.2 t/ha). Sesbania contained 97 kg N/ha, sunn hemp 101 kg N, cowpea 75 kg N and mungbean 65 kg N. Mungbean also produced 600 kg beans/ha. Maize fodder yielded 5.8 t dry matter/ha and removed 70 kg N/ha from the soil.

When no fertilizer N was applied, rice grain yields with sesbania, sunn hemp, and cowpea were similar and averaged 15% higher than with mungbean residue and 141% higher than fallow treatments (Table 1). With 60 kg N/ha, rice grain yield with all green manure crops and with mungbean residue were on a par, 36-48% higher than fallow plots. These yields were comparable with yields from fallow plots receiving 180 kg N/ha.

None of the green manure crops

incorporated in rice exhibited residual effects on the succeeding wheat crop (Table 2). Wheat yield in fallow plots with 120 kg N/ha was significantly

higher than in green manured plots supplied with 90 kg N/ha. Wheat yield after maize fodder was no different from that in fallow plots. □

Intercropping rice and pigeonpea

P.K. Mahapatra, N. Hati, and D. Satpathy, Orissa University of Agriculture and Technology, Bhubaneswar 751003, Orissa, India

The response of pigeonpea + rice to varying levels of N was studied in a randomized block design replicated four times during the 1984 and 1985 wet seasons in a lateritic soil of sandy loam texture (pH 5.3, 0.04% total N, 8 kg available P/ha, 125 kg available K/ha, CEC 3.8 meq/100 g).

Pigeonpea cultivar R-60 (180 d) was sown as the base crop in twin rows with an inter-twin-row distance of 90 cm and plant-to-plant spacing of 30 cm. Spacing and seed rate (20 kg/ha) for pigeonpea alone and intercropped pigeonpea were the same.

Rice cultivar DR-92 (90 d) was direct seeded in 15-cm rows in the interspace

of 90 cm. Row spacing for rice alone was 15 cm. Rice alone was sown at 100 kg seed/ha and intercropped rice at 75 kg seed/ha. Row ratio of pigeonpea to rice was 25 and the land area ratio was 1:0.75.

N was applied at 30, 45, 60, and 75 kg/ha; 10 kg N of each N level, plus 18 kg P and 17 kg K were applied at sowing for rice alone and the intercrops. The remaining N was applied to rice in 2 equal splits at 20 and 40 d after seeding. Pigeonpea alone received a single basal dose of 20-18-17 kg NPK/ha.

Intercropped rice showed no response to N. Mean grain yields were 2.0 t/ha for rice alone and 1.2 t/ha for intercropped rice. Mean yields of pigeonpea were 1.3 t/ha for the monocrop and 1.1 t/ha for the intercrop. The mean land equivalent ratio was 1.4, indicating considerable increase in resource use efficiency. □

Response of rice to NPK in long-term jute - rice - wheat sequence

B. C. Mandal and B. P. Sarkar, Jute Agricultural Research Institute, Barrackpore 743101, West Bengal, India

Table 1. NPK applied to jute - rice - wheat cropping sequence. Barrackpore, West Bengal, India, 1972-84.

Treatment	NPK (kg/ha)					
	Rice and wheat			Jute		
	N	P	K	N	P	K
T1 50% optimum ^a NPK	60	13	25	30	6.5	25
T2 100% optimum NPK	120	26	50	60	13.0	50
T3 150% optimum NPK	180	39	75	90	19.5	75
T4 100% NPK + hand weeding	120	26	50	60	13.0	50
T5 100% NPK + ZnSO ₄ for wheat only	120	26	50	60	13.0	50
T6 100% optimum NP	120	26	—	60	13.0	—
T7 100% optimum N	120	—	—	60	—	—
T8 100% NPK + farmyard manure for jute only	120	26	50	60	13.0	50
T9 100% optimum NPK + chemical weeding	120	26	50	60	13.0	50
T10 Control (no fertilizer)	—	—	—	—	—	—

^aOptimum NPK based on initial soil test.

The cropping sequence jute - rice - wheat is widely practiced in the eastern region of India, especially in the New Gangetic alluvial tracts. We laid out a long-term fertilizer experiment on 1 ha of recent